

On Generalization Of Generalized Star Generalized Continuous Function In Topological Spaces

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we defined and study a new class of continuous function namely generalization of generalized star generalized continuous function (briefly $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function) in topological spaces and further we studied the concept of $(gg)^*g$ – continuous function and some of its aspects are investigated.

Keywords: $(gg)^*g$ - closed sets, $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

INTRODUCTION

In this paper our aim is to study a based on $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function. The family of continuous function plays an important role in topology. Observing these, Csaszar introduced the concept of generalized open sets [10]. In 1970, Levin [29] introduced the concept of generalized closed sets and discussed about the properties of sets, closed and open maps, normal and separation axioms, compactness. In 1982, Malghan [22] introduced and studied the concept of generalized closed maps. In 2017, Basavaraj M. Ittanagi and H.G Govardhana Reddy [3] introduced gg -closed sets in topological spaces. In 2018, I. Christal Bai and T. Shyla Isac Mary [9] introduced $(gg)^*$ - closed sets in topological spaces. In 2026, X. Josphine Selva Rani and T. Shyla Isac Mary [20] introduced $(gg)^*g$ – closed sets in topological spaces. The aim of this paper is to be continue the study of $(gg)^*g$ – continuous function and analyzed the different aspects.

PRELIMINARIES

Throughout this paper always means the topological spaces (X, τ) and (Y, σ) on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. For a subset A of a topological space (X, τ) , the closure of A and the interior of A are denoted by $cl(A)$ and $int(A)$

respectively, A^c denotes the compliment of A in (X, τ) .

Definition:1

The closure of a subset A of a topological space (X, τ) is the smallest closed set containing A is denoted by $cl(A)$.

The generalized closure (briefly g - closure) of a subset A of a topological space (X, τ) is the smallest g - closed set containing A is denoted by $gcl(A)$.

Definition:2

Generalized - closed set (briefly g - closed) if $cl(A) \subseteq U$ [29] whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open in X .

Generalization of generalized closed set (briefly gg - closed) if $gcl(A) \subseteq U$ [3] whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is regular semi - open in X .

Generalization of generalized star closed set (briefly $(gg)^*$ - closed) if $rcl(A) \subseteq U$ [9] whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is gg - open in X .

Generalization of generalized star generalized closed set (briefly $(gg)^*g$ - closed) if $gcl(A) \subseteq U$ [20] whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $(gg)^*$ - open in (X, τ) .

Definition:3

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A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is called

- (i) Continuous [30] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is closed in (X, τ) .
- (ii) regular continuous [31] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is regular closed in (X, τ) .
- (iii) π - continuous function [14] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is π - closed in (X, τ) .
- (iv) g^* - continuous function [32] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is g^* - closed in (X, τ) .
- (v) $(gar)^{**}$ - continuous function [39] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is $(gar)^{**}$ - closed in (X, τ) .
- (vi) gr^* - continuous function [17] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is gr^* - closed in (X, τ) .
- (vii) $(gg)^*$ - continuous function [9] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is $(gg)^*$ - closed in (X, τ) .
- (viii) $r\beta$ - continuous function [23] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is $r\beta$ - closed in (X, τ) .
- (ix) gp^* - continuous function [18] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is gp^* - closed in (X, τ) .
- (x) $(gsp)^*$ - continuous function [33] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is $(gsp)^*$ - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xi) $g^\#$ - continuous function [4] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is $g^\#$ - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xii) $(gs)^*$ - continuous function [1] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is $(gs)^*$ - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xiii) g^*sr - continuous function [43] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is g^*sr - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xiv) r^*g^* - continuous function [27] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is r^*g^* - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xv) $(g^*p)^*$ - continuous function [34] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is $(g^*p)^*$ - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xvi) $r^\wedge g$ - continuous function [37] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is $r^\wedge g$ - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xvii) rwg - continuous function [26] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is rwg - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xviii) R^* - Continuous function [4] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is R^* - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xix) g^*p - Continuous function [38] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is g^*p - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xx) g^*s^* - Continuous function [1] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is g^*s^* - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xxi) strongly g^* - Continuous function [32] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is strongly g^* - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xxii) g^*s - Continuous function [43] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is g^*s - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xxiii) wg - Continuous function [26] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is wg - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xxiv) pg - Continuous function [18] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is pg - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xxv) ws - Continuous function [12] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is ws - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xxvi) gp - Continuous function [13] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is gp - closed in (X, τ) .

- (xxvii) αg - Continuous function [24] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is αg - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xxviii) gs - Continuous function [36] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is gs - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xxix) gsp - Continuous function [33] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is gsp - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xxx) sg - Continuous function [24] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is sg - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xxxii) $g\alpha$ - Continuous function [21] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is $g\alpha$ - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xxxiii) α - Continuous function [42] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is α - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xxxiv) b - Continuous function [11] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is b - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xxxv) $semi$ - Continuous function [8] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is $semi$ - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xxxvi) gb - Continuous function [40] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is gb - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xxxvii) gb^* - Continuous function [45] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is gb^* - closed in (X, τ) .
- (xxxviii) g^*s - Continuous function [1] if the inverse image of every closed set V in (Y, σ) is g^*s - closed in (X, τ) .

1. On Generalization of Generalized star generalized continuous function in Topological Spaces

Definition:1.1

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is called $(gg)^*g$ -continuous if the inverse image of

every closed set V in (Y, σ) is $(gg)^*g$ - closed set in (X, τ) .

Proposition:1.2

Every continuous function is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

Proof:

Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a continuous function and let V be a closed set in (Y, σ) .

Since f is continuous, then by Definition 3[i], $f^{-1}(V)$ is closed in (X, τ) . By Proposition 3.3[20], every closed set is $(gg)^*g$ - closed. So $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Definition 1.1, f is $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function.

Remark: The converse part of the above proposition need not be true as shown in the following example.

Example:1.3

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$, $\sigma = \{\emptyset, \{c, d\}, \{a, c\}, Y\}$

and $\tau_c = \{\emptyset, \{b, c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{c, d\}, X\}$. A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = c, f(b) = a, f(c) = b, f(d) = d$. f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{c, d\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a, d\}$, $\{a, d\}$ is not closed in (X, τ) .

Proposition:1.4

Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a function

- (i) Every regular continuous function is $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function.
- (ii) Every π - continuous function is $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function.
- (iii) Every g^* - continuous function is $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function.
- (iv) Every $(gar)^{**}$ - continuous function is $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function.
- (v) Every $(gr)^*$ - continuous function is $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function.

- (vi) Every $(gg)^*$ - continuous function is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.
- (vii) Every $r\beta$ - continuous function is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.
- (viii) Every gp^* - continuous function is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.
- (ix) Every $(gsp)^*$ - continuous function is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.
- (x) Every $g^\#$ - continuous function is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.
- (xi) Every $(gs)^*$ - continuous function is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.
- (xii) Every g^*sr - continuous function is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.
- (xiii) Every r^*g^* - continuous function is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.
- (xiv) Every $(g^*p)^*$ - continuous function is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

Proof:

- (i) Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a regular continuous function and let V be a

closed set in (X, τ) . Since f is regular continuous function, then by Definition 3[ii], $f^{-1}(V)$ is regular closed in (X, τ) . By Proposition 3.3[20], every regular closed set is $(gg)^*g$ - closed. Then $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Definition 1.1, f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

- (ii) Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a π - continuous function and let V be a

closed set in (X, τ) . Since f is π - continuous function, then by Definition 3[iii], $f^{-1}(V)$ is a π - closed in (X, τ) . By Proposition 3.3[20], every π - closed set is $(gg)^*g$ - closed. Then $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Definition 1.1, f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

- (iii) Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a g^* - continuous function and let V be a

closed set in (Y, σ) . Since f is g^* - continuous, then by Definition 3[iv], $f^{-1}(V)$ is g^* - closed in (X, τ) . By Proposition 3.3[20], every g^* - closed set is $(gg)^*g$ - closed. So $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Definition 1.1, f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

- (iv) Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a $(gar)^{**}$ - continuous function and let V

be a closed set in (X, σ) . Since f is $(gar)^{**}$ - continuous, then by Definition 3[v], $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gar)^{**}$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Proposition 3.3[20], every $(gar)^{**}$ - closed set is $(gg)^*g$ - closed. So $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Definition 1.1, f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

- (v) Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a $(gr)^*$ - continuous function and let V be a

closed set in (Y, σ) . Since f is $(gr)^*$ - continuous, then by Definition 3[vi], $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gr)^*$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Proposition 3.3[20], every $(gr)^*$ - closed set is $(gg)^*g$ - closed. So $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Definition 1.1, f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

- (vi) Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a $(gg)^*$ - continuous function and let V be a

closed set in (Y, σ) . Since f is $(gg)^*$ - continuous, then by Definition 3[vii], $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Proposition 3.3[20], every $(gg)^*$ - closed set is $(gg)^*g$ - closed. So $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Definition 1.1, f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

- (vii) Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a $r\beta$ - continuous function and let V be a

closed set in (Y, σ) . Since f is $r\beta$ - continuous, then by Definition 3[viii], $f^{-1}(V)$ is $r\beta$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Proposition 3.3[20], every $r\beta$ - closed set is $(gg)^*g$ - closed. So $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Definition 1.1, f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

- (viii) Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a gp^* - continuous function and let V be a

closed set in (Y, σ) . Since f is gp^* - continuous, then by Definition 3[ix], $f^{-1}(V)$ is gp^* - closed in (X, τ) .

By Proposition 3.3[20], every gp^* - closed set is $(gg)^*g$ - closed. So $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Definition 1.1, f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

(ix) Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a $(gsp)^*$ - continuous function and let V be a

closed set in (Y, σ) . Since f is $(gsp)^*$ - continuous, then by Definition 3[x], $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gsp)^*$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Proposition 3.3[20], every $(gsp)^*$ - closed set is $(gg)^*g$ - closed. So $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) . By definition 1.1, f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

(x) Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a $g^\#$ - continuous function and let V be a

closed set in (Y, σ) . Since f is $g^\#$ - continuous, then by Definition 3[xi], $f^{-1}(V)$ is $g^\#$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Proposition 3.3[20], every $g^\#$ - closed set is $(gg)^*g$ - closed. So $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Definition 1.1, f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

(xi) Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a $(gs)^*$ - continuous function and let V be a

closed set in (Y, σ) . Since f is $(gs)^*$ - continuous, then by Definition 3[xii], $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gs)^*$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Proposition 3.3[20], every $(gs)^*$ - closed set is $(gg)^*g$ - closed. So $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Definition 1.1, f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

(xii) Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a g^*sr - continuous function and let V be a

closed set in (Y, σ) . Since f is g^*sr - continuous, then by Definition 3[xiii], $f^{-1}(V)$ is g^*sr - closed in (X, τ) . By Proposition 3.3[20], every g^*sr - closed set is $(gg)^*g$ - closed. So $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Definition 1.1, f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

(xiii) Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a r^*g^* - continuous function and let V be a

closed set in (Y, σ) . Since f is r^*g^* - continuous, then by Definition 3[xiv], $f^{-1}(V)$ is r^*g^* - closed in (X, τ) . By proposition 3.3[20], every r^*g^* - closed set is $(gg)^*g$ - closed. So $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed in

(X, τ) . By Definition 1.1, f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

(xiv) Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a $(g^*p)^*$ - continuous function and let V be a

closed set in (Y, σ) . Since f is $(g^*p)^*$ - continuous then by Definition 3[xv], $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(g^*p)^*$ - closed in (X, τ) . By proposition 3.3[20], every $(g^*p)^*$ - closed set is $(gg)^*g$ - closed. So $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Definition 1.1, f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

Remark: The converse of the above proposition need not be true as shown in the following examples.

Example:1.5

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$, $\sigma = \{\varphi, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, Y\}$

and $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b\}, X\}$. A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = a, f(b) = d, f(c) = b, f(d) = c$. f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not regular continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a, b, c\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a, c, d\}$, $\{a, c, d\}$ is not regular closed in (X, τ) .

Example:1.6

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$, $\sigma = \{\varphi, \{c, d\}, \{a, c\}, Y\}$

and $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{b, c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{c, d\}, X\}$. An identity function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = a, f(b) = b, f(c) = c, f(d) = d$. By f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not π and g^* - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a, d\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a, d\}$, $\{a, d\}$ is not π and g^* - closed in (X, τ) .

Example:1.7

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c, d\}, Y\}$ and $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b\}, X\}$.

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = b, f(b) = d, f(c) = b, f(d) = c$. f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not $(gar)^{**}$ - continuous

function, because for closed set $V = \{a, b, c\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{b, c, d\}$, $\{b, c, d\}$ is not $(gar)^{**}$ -closed in (X, τ) .

Example:1.8

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$, $\sigma = \{\varphi, \{b\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$.

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = b, f(b) = a, f(c) = b, f(c) = c$. By f is $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function but not $(gr)^*$ and r^*g^* -continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a\}$, $\{a\}$ is not $(gr)^*$ and r^*g^* -closed in (X, τ) .

Example:1.9

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$, $\sigma = \{\varphi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, Y\}$

and $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b\}, X\}$. A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = c, f(b) = d, f(c) = a, f(d) = b$. f is $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function but not $(gg)^*$ -continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a, b\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{c, d\}$, $\{c, d\}$ is not $(gg)^*$ -closed in (X, τ) .

Example:1.10

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{a\}, \{b\}, Y\}$ and $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b\}, X\}$. A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = b, f(b) = d, f(c) = b, f(d) = c$. f is $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function but not $r\beta$ -continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a\}$, $\{a\}$ is not $r\beta$ -closed in (X, τ) .

Example:1.11

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{a\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b\}, X\}$. A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = c, f(b) = d, f(c) = b, f(d) = a$. f is $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function but not gs^* , gp^* , g^*sr and $(gsp)^*$ -continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{c, d\}$

in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a, b\}$, $\{a, b\}$ is not gs^* , gp^* , g^*sr and $(gsp)^*$ -closed in (X, τ) .

Example:1.12

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{a\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, d\}, \{a\}, X\}$. A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = a, f(b) = d, f(c) = c, f(d) = b$. f is $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function but not $g^\#$ and $(g^*p)^*$ -continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{c, d\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a, b\}$, $\{a, b\}$ is not $g^\#$ and $(g^*p)^*$ -closed in (X, τ) .

Proposition:1.13

Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a function

- (i) Every $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function is $r^\wedge g$ -continuous.
- (ii) Every $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function is rwg -continuous.

Proof:

- (i) Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function and let V be a

closed set in (Y, σ) . Since f is $(gg)^*g$ -continuous, then by Definition 3[xvi], $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ -closed in (X, τ) . By Proposition 3.3[20], every $(gg)^*g$ -closed set is $r^\wedge g$ -closed. So $f^{-1}(V)$ is $r^\wedge g$ -closed in (X, τ) . By Definition 1.1, f is $r^\wedge g$ -continuous function.

- (ii) Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function and let V be a

closed set in (Y, σ) . Since f is $(gg)^*g$ -continuous, then by Definition 3[xvii], $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ -closed in (X, τ) . By Proposition 3.3[20], every $(gg)^*g$ -closed set is rwg -closed. So $f^{-1}(V)$ is rwg -closed in (X, τ) . By Definition 1.1, f is rwg -continuous function.

Remark: The converse part of the proposition need not be true as shown in the following examples.

Example:1.14

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau =$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a, c\}$, $\{a, c\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ -closed in (X, τ) .
 $\{\varphi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, c, d\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c =$ A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = d, f(b) = b, f(c) = a, f(d) = c$.
 $\{\varphi, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, d\}, \{a\}, X\}$,

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = d, f(b) = b, f(c) = a, f(d) = c$. f is $r^\wedge g$ -continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a, b\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{b, c\}$, $\{b, c\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ -closed in (X, τ) .
 f is $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function but not R^* -continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a, b\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{b, c\}$, $\{b, c\}$ is not R^* -closed in (X, τ) .

Example:1.15

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau =$
 $\{\varphi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c =$
 $\{\varphi, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, d\}, \{a\}, X\}$. A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = b, f(b) = c, f(c) = d, f(d) = a$. f is $r^\wedge g$ -continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{d\}$, $\{d\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ -closed in (X, τ) .

2. Independent set of $(gg)^*g$ - continuous functions with other continuous function

The following example shows that the concept of $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function is independent from R^* -Continuous, g^*p -Continuous, g^*s^* -Continuous, strongly g^* -Continuous, g^*s -Continuous, wg -Continuous, pg -Continuous, ws -Continuous, gp -Continuous, ag -Continuous, gs -Continuous, gsp -Continuous, sg -Continuous, $g\alpha$ -Continuous, α -Continuous, b -Continuous, *semi*-Continuous, gb -Continuous, gb^* -Continuous, $g^\wedge s$ -Continuous.

Example:2.1

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau =$
 $\{\varphi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, c, d\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c =$
 $\{\varphi, \{b, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b\}, \{b\}, X\}$.

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = a, f(b) = c, f(c) = b, f(d) = d$.

f is R^* -continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a, b\}$

Example:2.2

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau =$
 $\{\varphi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c =$
 $\{\varphi, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b\}, X\}$.

An identity function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = a, f(b) = b, f(c) =$

$c, f(d) = d$. f is $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function but not g^*p -continuous

function, because for closed set $V = \{a, c, d\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a, c, d\}$. $\{a, c, d\}$ is not g^*p -closed in (X, τ) .

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = d, f(b) = b, f(c) = c, f(d) = a$.

f is g^*p -continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{d\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a\}$, $\{a\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ -closed in (X, τ) .

Example:2.3

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau =$
 $\{\varphi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{a\}, \{d\}, \{a, b, c\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c =$
 $\{\varphi, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, d\}, \{a\}, X\}$.

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = d, f(b) = a, f(c) = b, f(d) = c$.

f is $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function but not g^*s^* -continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a, b, c\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{b, c, d\}$. $\{b, c, d\}$ is not g^*s^* -closed in (X, τ) .

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = b, f(b) = d, f(c) = c, f(d) = a$.

f is g^*s^* - continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{d\}$ in $(Y, \sigma), f^{-1}(V) = \{b\}, \{b\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Example:2.4

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}, \tau = \{\varphi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\},$

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{c\}, \{a, b, c\}, Y\}, \tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b\}, X\}.$

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = a, f(b) = d, f(c) = c, f(d) = b$.

f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not strongly g^* - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a, b, c\}$ in $(Y, \sigma), f^{-1}(V) = \{a, c, d\}. \{a, c, d\}$ is not strongly g^* - closed in (X, τ) .

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = c, f(b) = d, f(c) = b, f(d) = a$.

f is strongly g^* - continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{c\}$ in $(Y, \sigma), f^{-1}(V) = \{a\}, \{a\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Example:2.5

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}, \tau = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\},$

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{a, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, Y\}, \tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, d\}, \{a\}, X\}.$

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = a, f(b) = b, f(c) = d, f(d) = c$.

f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not g^*s - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a, b, d\}$ in $(Y, \sigma), f^{-1}(V) = \{a, b, c\}. \{a, b, c\}$ is not g^*s - closed in (X, τ) .

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = c, f(b) = d, f(c) = b, f(d) = a$.

f is g^*s - continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b\}$ in

$(Y, \sigma), f^{-1}(V) = \{c\}, \{c\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Example:2.6

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}, \tau = \{\varphi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\},$

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{a, c, d\}, Y\}, \tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b\}, X\}.$

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = b, f(b) = a, f(c) = c, f(d) = d$.

f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not wg - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a, c, d\}$ in $(Y, \sigma), f^{-1}(V) = \{b, c, d\}. \{b, c, d\}$ is not wg - closed in (X, τ) .

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = b, f(b) = d, f(c) = c, f(d) = a$.

f is wg - continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b\}$ in $(Y, \sigma), f^{-1}(V) = \{a\}, \{a\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Example:2.7

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}, \tau = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\},$

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, Y\}, \tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, d\}, \{a\}, X\}.$

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = a, f(b) = d, f(c) = b, f(d) = c$.

f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not pg - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a, d\}$ in $(Y, \sigma), f^{-1}(V) = \{a, b\}. \{a, b\}$ is not pg - closed in (X, τ) .

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}, \tau = \{\varphi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\},$

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, Y\}, \tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b\}, X\}.$

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = c, f(b) = b, f(c) = b, f(d) = d$.

f is pg - continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{d\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{d\}$, $\{d\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Example:2.8

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$,
 $\sigma = \{\varphi, \{a\}\{b, c, d\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b\}, X\}$.

An identity function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = a, f(b) = b, f(c) =$

$c, f(d) = d$. f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not ws - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b, c, d\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{b, c, d\}$. $\{b, c, d\}$ is not ws - closed in (X, τ) .

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = c, f(b) = b, f(c) = a, f(d) = d$.

f is ws - continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{c\}$, $\{c\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Example:2.9

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$,
 $\sigma = \{\varphi, \{b\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{c, d\}\{a, d\}, \{a\}, X\}$.

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = d, f(b) = a, f(c) = b, f(d) = c$.

f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not gp - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{c\}$. $\{c\}$ is not gp - closed in (X, τ) .

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$,
 $\sigma = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{a, d\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b\}, X\}$.

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = b, f(b) = d, f(c) = a, f(d) = c$.

f is gp - continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a\}$, $\{a\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Example:2.10

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$,
 $\sigma = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{d\}, \{b, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{c, d\}\{a, d\}, \{a\}, X\}$.

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = d, f(b) = b, f(c) = c, f(d) = a$.

f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not ag - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b, d\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a, b\}$. $\{a, b\}$ is not ag - closed in (X, τ) .

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{b, d\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b\}, X\}$.

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = b, f(b) = a, f(c) = c, f(d) = d$.

f is ag - continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a\}$, $\{a\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Example:2.11

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{d\}, \{b, d\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{c, d\}\{a, d\}, \{a\}, X\}$.

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = d, f(b) = b, f(c) = a, f(d) = c$.

f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not gs - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{b\}$. $\{b\}$ is not gs - closed in (X, τ) .

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = b, f(b) = d, f(c) = c, f(d) = a$.

f is gs - continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b, d\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a, b\}$, $\{a, b\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Example:2.12

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{b, c, d\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, d\}, \{a\}, X\}$.

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = b, f(b) = a, f(c) = c, f(d) = d$.

f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not gsp - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a\}$. $\{a\}$ is not gsp - closed in (X, τ) .

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{b, d\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, d\}, \{a\}, X\}$.

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = c, f(b) = b, f(c) = a, f(d) = d$.

f is αg - continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{b\}$, $\{b\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Example:2.13

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{a\}, \{a, b, c\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, d\}, \{a\}, X\}$.

An identity function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = a, f(b) = b, f(c) =$

$c, f(d) = d$. f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not sg - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a, b, c\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a, b, c\}$. $\{a, b, c\}$ is not sg - closed in (X, τ) .

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = c, f(b) = d, f(c) = a, f(d) = b$.

f is sg - continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{c\}$, $\{c\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Example:2.14

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{b, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b\}, \{b\}, X\}$.

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = b, f(b) = c, f(c) = a, f(d) = d$.

f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not $g\alpha$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b, c\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a, b\}$. $\{a, b\}$ is not $g\alpha$ - closed in (X, τ) .

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = c, f(b) = d, f(c) = a, f(d) = b$.

f is $g\alpha$ - continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{d\}$, $\{d\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Example:2.15

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, c\}, \{b\}, X\}$,

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = c, f(b) = b, f(c) = a$.

f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not α - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a, b\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{b, c\}$. $\{b, c\}$ is not α - closed in (X, τ) .

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{a\}, \{b, d\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, d\}, \{a\}, X\}$.

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = d, f(b) = c, f(c) = b, f(d) = a$.

f is α - continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{d\}$, $\{d\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Example:2.16

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c, d\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b\}, X\}$.

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = b, f(b) = a, f(c) = c, f(d) = d$.

f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not b - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b, c, d\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a, c, d\}$. $\{b, c, d\}$ is not b - closed in (X, τ) .

f is b - continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a\}$, $\{a\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Example:2.17

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{b, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b\}, \{b\}, X\}$.

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = a, f(b) = c, f(c) = b, f(d) = d$.

f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not semi continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b, c\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{b, c\}$. $\{b, c\}$ is not semi closed in (X, τ) .

f is semi continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a\}$, $\{a\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Example:2.18

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{b, c, d\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b\}, \{b\}, X\}$.

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = c, f(b) = a, f(c) = b, f(d) = d$.

f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not gb^* and gb continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b, c, d\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{a, c, d\}$. $\{a, c, d\}$ is not gb^* and gb - closed in (X, τ) .

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = b, f(b) = d, f(c) = c, f(d) = a$.

f is gb^* and gb - continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{b\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{c\}$, $\{c\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Example:2.19

Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\varphi, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$,

$\sigma = \{\varphi, \{a\}, \{a, b, d\}, Y\}$, $\tau_c = \{\varphi, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, d\}, \{a\}, X\}$.

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = c, f(b) = a, f(c) = b, f(d) = d$.

f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not $g^{\wedge*s}$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a, b, d\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{b, c, d\}$. $\{b, c, d\}$ is not $g^{\wedge*s}$ - closed in (X, τ) .

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is defined by $f(a) = c, f(b) = a, f(c) = d, f(d) = b$.

f is $g^{\wedge*s}$ - continuous function but not $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{a\}$ in (Y, σ) , $f^{-1}(V) = \{b\}$, $\{b\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Remark: From the above discussion and known results for the relationship between $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function and other existing continuous function are established in figure 1.

Figure 1

In the Figure 1, $A \rightarrow B$ means the set A implies B, but not conversely.

In the Figure 2, $A \leftrightarrow B$ means the set A and B are independent of each other.

Figure 2

3. Aspects of $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function

Theorem:3.1 If $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function and

$g: (Y, \sigma) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ is continuous function then $(gof): (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

Proof:

Let us take U be any closed set in (Z, η) . Since g is continuous function then by

Definition 3[i], $g^{-1}(U)$ is closed in (Y, σ) . Since f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function then by Definition 1.1, $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(U))$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed set in (X, τ) . Therefore $(gof)^{-1}(U)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed set in (X, τ) . Hence (gof) is $(gg)^*g$ -continuous function.

Remark: Composition of two $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function need not be $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

Example:3.2

Let $X = Y = Z = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$

$\sigma = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, Y\}$. A functions $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ and $g: (Y, \sigma) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ are defined by $f(a) = a, f(b) = b, f(c) = c, f(d) = d$ and $g(a) = a, g(b) = b, g(c) = d, g(d) = c$. f and g are $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function but not $(gof)^{-1}$ is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, because for closed set $V = \{c, d\}$ in (Y, σ) , $(gof)^{-1}(V) = \{c, d\}$. $\{c, d\}$ is not $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) .

Theorem:3.3

A function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$. Then the following statements are equivalent.

- (i) f is $(gg)^*g$ – continuous function.
- (ii) $f^{-1}(U)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – open set in (X, τ) for every open set U in (Y, σ) .
- (iii) $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – closed set in (X, τ) for every closed set V in (Y, σ) .

Proof:

(i)⇒(ii) Let f be a $(gg)^*g$ – continuous function and U be an open set in (Y, σ) . Then U^c is closed set in (Y, σ) . Since f is $(gg)^*g$ – continuous function, by Definition 1.1, $f^{-1}(U^c)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – closed set in (X, τ) . Therefore $f^{-1}(U^c) = X - f^{-1}(U)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – closed set in (X, τ) and hence $f^{-1}(U)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – open set in (X, τ) .

(ii)⇒(iii) Let us assume that $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – open set in (X, τ) for every open set U in (Y, σ) . Let V be a closed set in (Y, σ) . Then V^c is open set in (Y, σ) .

By assumption $f^{-1}(V^c)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – open set in (X, τ) . Therefore $f^{-1}(V^c) = X - f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – open set in (X, τ) and hence $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – closed set in (X, τ) .

(ii)⇒(iii) Let f be a $(gg)^*g$ – continuous function and let V be a closed set in (Y, σ) . Then V^c is open set in (Y, σ) . Since f is $(gg)^*g$ – continuous function, by Definition 1.1, $f^{-1}(V^c) = X - f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – open set in (X, τ) . Hence $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – closed set in (X, τ) .

(iii)⇒(i) Let us assume that $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – closed set in (X, τ) for every closed set V in (Y, σ) . Let W be an open set in (Y, σ) , then W^c is closed set in (Y, σ) . By assumption $f^{-1}(W^c)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – closed set in (X, τ) . Therefore $f^{-1}(W^c) = X - f^{-1}(W)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – closed set in (X, τ) and hence f is $(gg)^*g$ – continuous function.

Theorem:3.4

Let (X, τ) be a topological space in which every singleton set is $(gg)^*$ – closed.

Then the function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – continuous if $x \in gint(f^{-1}(V))$ for every open subset V of (Y, σ) containing $f(x)$.

Proof:

Assume that a function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – continuous function.

To prove $x \in gint(f^{-1}(V))$. Let $x \in X$ and V be an open set in (Y, σ) containing $f(x)$. That is $f(x) \in V$. Since f is $(gg)^*g$ – continuous function, by Theorem 3.3 $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – open set in (X, τ) and since $\{x\}$ is $(gg)^*$ – closed, then $x \in gint(f^{-1}(V))$.

Conversely assume that $x \in gint(f^{-1}(V))$ for every open subset V of (Y, σ) containing $f(x)$. To prove f is $(gg)^*g$ – continuous function.

Let V be an open set in (Y, σ) . Suppose that $G \subseteq f^{-1}(V)$ and G is $(gg)^*g$ – closed. Let $x \in G \subseteq f^{-1}(V)$

$$\Rightarrow x \in f^{-1}(V)$$

$$\Rightarrow f(x) \in V$$

By hypothesis, $x \in gint(f^{-1}(V))$ and from the assumption $f^{-1}(V)$ is an $(gg)^*g$ – open set in (X, τ) . By Theorem 3.3, f is $(gg)^*g$ – continuous function.

Theorem:3.5

If f is $(gg)^*g$ – continuous function then $f((gg)^*g cl(A)) \subseteq cl(f(A))$ for every subset A of (X, τ) .

Proof:

Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is $(gg)^*g$ – continuous function and let $A \subseteq X$ then $cl(f(A))$

is closed in (Y, σ) .

Since $f(A) \subseteq cl(f(A))$, $A \subseteq f^{-1}(cl(f(A)))$

We know that $cl(f(A))$ is closed in (Y, σ) and also f is $(gg)^*g$ – continuous function.

By Definition 1.1, $f^{-1}(cl(f(A)))$ is $(gg)^*g$ – closed in (X, τ) .

Let us assume that $y \in f^{-1}((gg)^*g - cl(A))$. Then $y = f(x)$, where $x \in (gg)^*g - cl(A)$. Let G be an

open set containing $y = f(x)$. Since f is $(gg)^*g -$ continuous function, by Theorem 3.3, $f^{-1}(G)$ is $(gg)^*g -$ open set in (X, τ) . By Theorem 5.8[20], $f^{-1}(G) \cap A \neq \varnothing$.

$$\begin{aligned} &\Rightarrow f(f^{-1}(G) \cap A) \neq \varnothing \\ &\Rightarrow f(f^{-1}(G)) \cap f(A) \neq \varnothing. \\ &f(f^{-1}(G)) \in G \\ &\Rightarrow G \cap f(A) \neq \varnothing. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $y \in cl(f(A))$ because for any open set G containing y , $G \cap f(A) \neq \varnothing$ is a characterization of y being in the closure of $f(A)$. Hence $f((gg)^*g - cl(A)) \subseteq cl(f(A))$.

Theorem:3.6

Let a function $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ then the following statements are equivalent.

- (i) For every point $x \in (X, \tau)$ and each open set V containing $f(x)$ in (Y, σ) , there is an

$(gg)^*g -$ open set U in (X, τ) such that $x \in U$ and $f(U) \subseteq V$.

- (ii) For each $A \subseteq (X, \tau)$, $f((gg)^*g - cl(A)) \subseteq cl f(A)$.

- (iii) For each $B \subseteq (X, \tau)$, $(gg)^*gcl(f^{-1}(B)) \subseteq f^{-1}(cl(B))$.

Proof:

(i)⇒(ii) Suppose (i) is hold. Let us assume that $y \in f((gg)^*g - cl(A))$. Then there exists an element $x \in (gg)^*g - cl(A)$ such that $y = f(x)$. Let V be an open set containing y that is $y \in V, f(x) \in V$. Since $x \in (gg)^*gcl(A)$, by Theorem 5.8[20], there exists an $(gg)^*g -$ open set U containing a point x such that $U \cap A \neq \varnothing$.

$$\begin{aligned} &\Rightarrow f(U \cap A) \neq \varnothing \\ &\Rightarrow f(U) \cap f(A) \neq \varnothing \end{aligned}$$

By hypothesis $f(U) \subseteq V$

$$\Rightarrow f(U) \cap f(A) \subseteq V \cap f(A) \neq \varnothing$$

$$\Rightarrow V \cap f(A) \neq \varnothing$$

Thus $y \in cl(f(A))$, because for any open set V containing y , $V \cap f(A) \neq \varnothing$ is a characterization of y being in the closure of $f(A)$.

$$\text{Therefore } f((gg)^*g - cl(A)) \subseteq cl(f(A)).$$

(ii)⇒(i) Suppose (ii) is hold. Let V be an open set containing $f(x)$ and let $x \in (X, \tau)$. And let $A = f^{-1}(V^c)$. Since $f((gg)^*g - cl(A)) \subseteq cl(f(A))$

$$\begin{aligned} &= cl((V^c)) \\ &= V^c \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Therefore } f((gg)^*gcl(A)) \subseteq V^c$$

$$\Rightarrow (gg)^*gcl(A) \subseteq f^{-1}(V^c) = A$$

$$\Rightarrow (gg)^*gcl(A) \subseteq A$$

Also we know that $A \subseteq (gg)^*gcl(A)$ that implies $(gg)^*gcl(A) = A$.

$$\text{Since } f(x) \in V, x \in f^{-1}(V)$$

$$\text{This } x \notin A \text{ then } x \notin (gg)^*gcl(A)$$

By Theorem 5.8[20], there exists $(gg)^*g$ open set U containing x such that $U \cap A \neq \varnothing$

$$\text{That implies } V \subseteq A^c \Rightarrow f(U) \subseteq f(A^c) \subseteq V.$$

$$\text{Hence } f(U) \subseteq V.$$

(ii)⇒(iii) Suppose (ii) is hold. Let $B \subseteq (Y, \sigma)$ and replacing A by $f^{-1}(B)$ in (ii).

$$\text{We get } f((gg)^*gcl(f^{-1}(B))) \subseteq cl(f(f^{-1}(B))) = cl(B)$$

$$\Rightarrow f((gg)^*gcl(f^{-1}(B))) \subseteq cl(B)$$

$$\Rightarrow (gg)^*gcl(f^{-1}(B)) \subseteq f^{-1}(cl(B))$$

(iii)⇒(ii) Suppose (iii) is hold. Let $A \subseteq (X, \sigma)$ and take $f(A) = B$ in (iii)

$$\text{We get } (gg)^*gcl(f^{-1}(f(A))) \subseteq f^{-1}(cl(f(A)))$$

$$\Rightarrow (gg)^*gcl(A) \subseteq f^{-1}(cl(f(A)))$$

$$\Rightarrow f((gg)^*gcl(A)) \subseteq cl(f(A)).$$

Theorem:3.7

If $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is closed and $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function and B is $(gg)^*g$ -

closed set of (y, σ) then $f^{-1}(B)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed set in (x, τ) .

Proof:

Let B be $(gg)^*g$ - closed set of (Y, σ) and let $f^{-1}(B) \subseteq U$, where U is an open set of

(X, τ) . Since f is closed, there is an open set V such that $B \subseteq V$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subseteq U$. Since B is $(gg)^*g$ - closed set $gcl(B) \subseteq U$, that implies $f^{-1}(gcl(B)) \subseteq U$. Since $gcl(B) \subseteq cl(B)$,

by assumption f is closed and $(gg)^*g$ - continuous, $f^{-1}(cl(B))$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed set in (X, τ) .

$$\Rightarrow gcl(f^{-1}(cl(B))) \subseteq U$$

$$\Rightarrow gcl(f^{-1}(B)) \subseteq U.$$

Therefore $f^{-1}(B)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed set in (X, τ) .

Theorem:3.8

If $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, closed and

$g: (Y, \sigma) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function then $gof: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

Proof:

Let us take U be any closed set in (Z, η) . Then $f^{-1}(U)$ is closed set in (Y, σ) .

Since g is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function and closed then $g^{-1}(U)$ is closed in (Y, σ) and also f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(U))$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed set in (X, τ) . Hence gof is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

Theorem:3.9

In extremely disconnected space (X, τ) , If $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is g - continuous function and open then $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

Proof:

Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a g-continuous function and let V be a

closed set in (X, τ) . Since f is g-continuous function and open, then $f^{-1}(V)$ is g-closed in (X, τ) . By Theorem 5.4[20], $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed, then $f^{-1}(V)$ is $(gg)^*g$ - closed in (X, τ) . By Definition 1.1, f is $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function.

CONCLUSION

The study of $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function in topological spaces literary investigated. The concept of $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function will be extended to strongly $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, perfectly $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function, contra $(gg)^*g$ - continuous function. Also this study can be elaborated to bitopological spaces and fuzzy topological spaces.

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